

ASSOCIATE FACTOR OF TRAFFICKING IN WOMEN AND CHILDREN IN CALABAR, CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

Trafficking in women and children is the illegal trade of human beings for the purposes of transfer, commercial sexual exploitation, forced labor and it is known as a modern-day form of slavery. Trafficking violates all known standards of human rights and dignity of human. It violates the right to health, right to liberty, right to equality and security of person. This study examines those associate factors of Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. The study specifically examined the extent to which lack of basic needs and unemployment relates to Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. A review of literature was carried out according to variables of the study. The study adopts the rational choice theory. This study adopted the survey design is selecting 151 samples from Calabar which was the study area using the purposive and snowballing sampling technique the instrument of data collection is the questionnaire. Data obtained from the questionnaire were interpreted, using statistical tools such as tables, simple percentages and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis. Results revealed that Lack of basic needs significantly correlate with Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. Results also revealed that there is a strong significant relationship between unemployment and Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. The study recommends that the governments should make efforts towards the reduction of lack of basic amenities in the land. Skill acquisition should be promoted and small loans be made available for eligible persons amongst others.

Keywords: Associate Factor, Trafficking in women and children, lack of basic needs, unemployment

1. Introduction

Trafficking in human is among the most disturbing issues globally today. Never a day goes by without news that bothers on human trafficking. It ranks among the most

prevailing transnational crime globally. Despite a lack of clear definition, it is mostly seen as a new form of international slave trade with the aim of making profits. Today human trafficking is a global business affecting mostly children and young adults especially women in less developed nations. The United State Department of State refers to human trafficking as including all of the criminal conduct involved in forced labour and sex trafficking, essentially the conduct involved in reducing or holding someone in compelled service (United States Department of State, 2013).

According to the United Nation (2000) human Trafficking refers to the recruitment, transportation, transfer, labouring or a receipt of persons, by means of threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, of abduction, of fraud, of deception, of the abuse of powers or of a position of vulnerability or of the giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person, for the purpose of exploitation, servitude and child labour. According to Ekpe (1986), human trafficking is the use of deceit and coercion to recruit and transfer persons either internally within the domestic borders of a country or externally across international borders for the purpose of exploitation.

The International Organization for Migration (IOM) and United Nation Office on Drugs and Crime report that the number of women trafficked have increased in both developed and developing nations (United Nations Office of Drugs and Crime, 2012). In In their study Bertone, (2000) and Cree (2008), women between the age of 18 and 25 are mostly the main targeted by traffickers, mostly in socio-economic disadvantaged areas. Estimating the global prevalence of human trafficking is due to its hidden nature (United Nations Office of Drugs and Crime, 2012; Ukwayi, Eja & Unwanede, 2012). But a recent estimate indicated that trafficking reaches between one and two million people each year worldwide; 60-70% of which are young girls (United Nations Office of Drugs and Crime, 2012; Cree, 2008). The International Labour Organisation (ILO) and the Walk Free Foundation (WFF) (2017) report estimates that 40 million people were victims of modern slavery in any given day in 2016. Out of these, approximately 25 million people were in forced labour and another 15 million people were in a forced marriage.

Nigeria is a nation for destination and transit of trafficking and has garnered a reputation for cross-border and internal trafficking. Human trafficking ranks as the third largest crime after drug trade and economic fraud. There is also evidence of internal trafficking. Destinations for trafficked Nigerians include the neighbouring West African countries (Côte d'Ivoire, Mali, Benin, Equatorial Guinea, Cameroon, Gabon and Guinea), European countries (Italy, Belgium, Spain, the Netherlands, Germany and the United Kingdom), North Africa (Libya, Algeria and Morocco) and Middle Eastern countries (Saudi Arabia). Recently, South America has also become a point of destination for trafficked persons, particularly Venezuela. Primarily women and girls, but also boys are trafficked for purposes of sexual exploitation, forced labour and organ harvesting.

United Nations Children Emergency Fund (1998) reported that more than 4000 children were trafficked from Cross River and Akwa Ibom States to other parts of the nation as well as been trafficked across the border to other nations. States such as Cross River, as well as Edo rank among the main providers of external trafficking in persons to Italy, Spain, Gabon, Benin Republic and Cameroon. When considering the cause of human trafficking, traffickers target the less privileged people with promises of higher incomes to improve economic situations, support parents and families in villages, and escape from war and conflict (Angioha, Nwagboso, Ironbar & Ishie, 2018; Agba, Agba, & Nwosu, 2015; Ukwayi, Angioha & Ojong-Ejoh, 2018; Ukwayi, Okpa & Akwaji, 2019). Studies have revealed that women and children are the key target group because of their marginalization in many societies, and their limited economic resources (Angioha & Ugal, 2019; Okpa & Ukwayi, 2017). This study seeks to answer the question, to what extent does Factors such as Lack of basic amenities and unemployment relates with Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria.

2. Objective of the Study

The objective of the study is to examine those associate factors of trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. The specific objectives includes to;

- Examine the relationship between lack of basic amenities and Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria.
- Assess the correlates between unemployment and Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria.

2.1 Statement of the Hypotheses

- There is no significant relationship between Lack of basic amenities and Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria.
- Unemployment does not significantly correlates with Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria.

2.2 Scope of the Study

The study aimed to examine those associate factors of trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. The study will study factors such as lack of basic amenities and unemployment as they influence trafficking. The study examined how social and environmental factors such as lack of basic amenities and unemployment influences women and child trafficking in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. The study will be carried out in three months and will focus on trafficking in Calabar Cross River State, Nigeria.

3. Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

3.1 Literature Review

The root causes of trafficking are various and often differ from one country to another. Trafficking is a complex phenomenon that is often driven or influenced by social, economic, cultural and other factors. Many of these factors are specific to individual trafficking patterns and to the States in which they occur. There are, however, many factors that tend to be common to trafficking in general or found in a wide range of different regions, patterns or cases Studies have focused on the factors that contribute to women and children trafficking (Ukwayi, Angioha & Nwagboso, 2018; Abdulraheem & Oladipo, 2010; Ukwayi & Igwe-Okomiso, 2018; Asefach, 2018; Murugan & Abebaw, 2014; Ukwayi, Akintola & Angioha, 2019; Iji, Ojong & Angioha, 2018).

Abdulraheem and Oladipo (2010) his study assessed the pattern of trafficking in women and children and factors influencing it. Quantitative and qualitative study designs were used. Women and children aged 15 - 49 and 10 - 14 years respectively constituted the study population. A multistage cluster sampling technique was used to select sample. Quantitative and qualitative methods were adopted. Among the interviewed women, 16.8% had experienced trafficking preceding the survey. The most frequent type of trafficking was commercial sex (46.7%) followed by child labour (34.5%). Educated and enlightened people (57.3%) appeared to be the main perpetrators of women and child trafficking followed by intimate/close associate (32.1%). Contributing factors for trafficking in women and children in this study are poverty (58.7%), parental discrimination favoring boys over girls (51.4%), lack of knowledge of human slavery and trafficking (33.6%) and family disintegration (21.5%) increase in school dropouts, lack of governments' monitoring of trade working environment and poor socio-economic conditions appeared to be significantly associated with trafficking in women and children ($p < 0.05$).

Asefach (2018) study focused on female victims of human trafficking from Ethiopia. The study the causes of trafficking and how it affects the social and emotional well-being of women. The study was conducted using a constructivist framework and involves in-depth interviews with five returnees whose experiences as victims are explored. The goal is to provide insight into the challenges faced by the wider population. Emergent themes in the stories are discussed in line with relevant literature. The study shows lack of job opportunities, limited income, and false promises made by brokers as the major factors drawing women into human trafficking. The findings also show that even after return, the victims experience further difficulties as a result of post-traumatic psychological factors.

Azage, Abeje and Mekonnen (2014) study was to assess sex trafficking awareness and associated factors among youth females in Bahir Dar town, North-West Ethiopia. A community based cross-sectional study design was employed to collect data from February 1st-30th 2012 from a total of 417 youth females. The participants in the study were selected using systematic random sampling techniques. A structured Amharic

questionnaire was used to collect data. Data were entered, cleaned and analyzed using SPSS 16.0. Descriptive statistics were used to describe data. Logistic regression analysis was used to identify factors associated with sex trafficking awareness. Two hundred forty-nine (60%) of the participants reported that they had heard or read about sex trafficking. Television (64%), friends (46%) and radio (39%) were the most frequently mentioned sources of information about sex trafficking. About 87% and 74% of the participants mentioned friends and brokers respectively as mediators of sex trafficking. Having TV at home (AOR=2.19, 95% CI: 1.31-3.67), completing grade 10 or more (AOR=2.22, 95% CI: 1.18-4.17), taking training on gender issues (AOR=3.59, 95% CI: 2.11-6.10) and living together with parents (AOR=3.65, 95% CI: 1.68-7.93) were factors found associated with sex trafficking awareness.

Murugan and Abebaw (2014) study assesses factors contributing to human trafficking and victimization and the contexts of vulnerability with reference to stranded victims in Metema, Ethiopia. Employing a cross-sectional qualitative research, primary data were gathered from various groups of purposely selected subjects: stranded victims, traffickers, law enforcing agents and social service providers. In-depth interviews, key-informant interviews, focus group discussions and non-participant observation were used as methods of acquiring information which was, finally, analyzed thematically to provide a qualitative account on the problem under study. The study found that victims highly pressured by various social structural factors (for instance, poverty, excessive social stress on economic success, the submission of non-economic institutions to the drives of economic calculations, the targets' bounded economic rationality, the expansion of migration/employment agencies and the effect of migration networks) towards migration which ultimately made them motivated targets of trafficking.

Adesina (2014) paper examines the nexus between poverty and child trafficking in the country. While most research on child trafficking, especially in Nigeria, has been concerned with trafficking across borders, this study fills a gap in the literature by focusing on child trafficking within the country. Utilizing the restricted opportunity theories, the paper argues that poverty and lack of parental support render children more vulnerable to being trafficked. Findings from the study showed that the root causes of child trafficking and the vulnerability of rural communities to trafficking are attributable to acute poverty, unemployment, ignorance and ineffectiveness of the legal framework for tackling trafficking in Nigeria.

In his study, Pearson (2003) conclude that harsh living conditions mostly characterized by unemployment, and a lack of opportunities in the countries of origin and, secondly, the demand that exists in the rich countries of the West is what make the business of human trafficking to be booming. Pearson explained further that it is under such circumstances that the victims are exploited as cheap labor in the restaurant trade or the sex industry through forced marriage and illegal adoption. Simply put, these are the push and pull factors

4. Theoretical Framework

The study adopts the rational choice theory. This theory adopts a utilitarian belief that man is a reasoning actor who weighs means and ends, costs and benefits, and makes a rational choice. Cornish and Clarke (1986) see crime as an event that occurs when an offender decides to risk breaking the law after considering his or her own need for money, personal values or learning experiences and how well a target is protected, how affluent the neighborhood is or how efficient the local police are. Before committing a crime, the reasoning criminal weighs the chances of getting caught, the severity of the expected penalty, the values to be gained by committing the act and his/her immediate need for that value. Keel (2007), in support of rational choice theory, posits that people have the freedom to choose what behaviours they engage in, and that they make those choices based on rational calculations.

The Rational Choice Theory of Cornish and Clarke (1986) was considered relevant to this study as it states that the offender risks breaking the law after considering his/her own need for money, personal values, learning experiences and how well a target is protected. Trafficking in women and children is an organized crime that involves a network of individuals, not a one man affair. Those that engage in this crime must have resolved within themselves to engage in it, and to them, their decision is rational. Motivated by the need for money and social gain, the individual engages in learning the skills and techniques for the crime, and so some extent, what the individual has learnt gives him confidence in his (rational) choice.

5. Materials and Method

This study adopted the survey design. Survey design was chosen because the study involved using selected samples from a segment of the population to analyze a large population at a given time (Obikeze, 1999; Ukwayi, Okpa, Adewoyin, Angioha, & Udom, 2017). The population of the study includes households in Calabar whose members have experienced trafficking. The population also include individuals living in the study area who knowledge on the social issue of human trafficking. The sample size used for this study was one hundred and fifty one (151) arrived at using the survey monkey sample determinant technique at 8% margin of error and 95% confidence level. The purposive and snowball sampling technique was used to selected the samples for the study from the study area. The purposive sampling technique was used to select four areas from Calabar. The area is Anantigha, Atimbo, Ekpo Abasi and Watts. From these areas forty nine (49) households each from each purposively selected area were selected using the snowballing sampling technique. The snowballing sampling technique was used because the researcher did not have knowledge of how to find all the respondents. The researcher located one household and member of that household was able to direct the researcher to other households that have suffered from trafficking. The relevant data for this study collected through the questionnaire. Data

obtained from the questionnaire were interpreted, using statistical tools such as tables, simple percentages and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis being a non-parametric inferential statistical technique was used to test the hypotheses of the study with a view to enabling the researcher draw valid conclusions on the hypotheses.

6. Data Presentation and Results

6.1 Data Presentation

In order to analyse the data, the raw scores of all the items in each variable was summed together to show a result for each variable. Data was analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program version 20. Results were presented in frequencies, percentages, charts and tables as well as inferential statistics as all hypotheses were tested using Pearson product moment correlation at 0.05 level of significance (i.e. 95% confidence interval).

Out of the 151 administered questionnaire for this study, only 118 respondents representing 78.6% returned questionnaire were properly filled without missing values and mutilation, therefore the said number was used for the data analysis. This moderate return rate was caused by the most families found it difficult to disclose sensitive information about their members,

As presented in Table 1, out of the 118 respondents used in this study, 64 (54.2%) were 26 - 35 years; 26 (22.0%) were 36 – 45 years; 21 (17.8%) were 25 years and below while only 7 (5.9%) were 46 years and above. This trend was expected, since the organization studied considers age at the time of employment. A graphical illustration is presented in figure 1.

Figure 1: Age of respondents

Also, Table 1 revealed respondents' demographic information. The responses to the questionnaire in respect to sex reveal that, most of the respondents 64 (54.2%) were

female while 54 (45.8%) were male. This result shows that, there are more female respondents in our sample and this is similar to the population, a graphical illustration is presented in figure 2.

Figure 2: Sex of respondents

Distribution of respondents based on marital status reveal that, most of the respondents 67 (56.8%) were married while 51 (43.2%) were single. This result could be so because of the age range of the respondents since there have attain the age of marriage and have source of income to keep a family. A graphical illustration is presented in figure 3.

Figure 3: Respondents' marital status

Table 1: Demographic data

Variable	Category	N	Percent (%)
Age of respondents	Below 25 years	21	17.8
	26-35 years	64	54.2
	36-45 years	26	22.0
	46 years and above	7	5.9
	Total	118	100.0
Sex	Male	54	45.8
	Female	64	54.2
	Total	118	100.0
Marital status	Single	67	56.8
	Married	51	43.2
	Total	118	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2019.

7. Data Analysis

7.1 Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between Lack of basic amenities and Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. The independent variable in this hypothesis is Lack of basic amenities while the dependent variable is Women and Children Trafficking. Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was used to test this hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance and the result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Pearson product moment correlation of Lack of basic amenities and Trafficking in women and children

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r-value	Sig.
Lack of basic amenities	118	18.63	2.96	0.334**	.000
Women and children trafficking	118	18.96	2.05		

*significant at 0.05 level; df = 116 critical r value = 0.098

Source: Field survey, 2019.

The result in Table 2 revealed that the calculated r – value of 0.334** is greater than the critical r-value of 0.098 at 0.05 level of significance with 116 degrees of freedom. By this result, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant relationship between Lack of basic amenities and Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted. The correlation coefficient is a standardized measure of an observed effect, it is a commonly used measure of the size of an effect and that values of ± 0.1 represent a small effect, ± 0.3 is a medium effect and ± 0.5 is a large effect

The squared correlation $(0.334)^2$ which is a measure of effect size indicates the proportion of explained variance on the dependent variable. Therefore, 11.1% of the variance in Trafficking in women and children is accounted for by lack of basic amenities. The magnitude of effect is moderate. We can conclude that, there is a

significant relationship between Lack of basic amenities and Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria.

7.2 Hypothesis Two

Unemployment does not significantly correlates with Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. The independent variable in this hypothesis is unemployment while the dependent variable is Women and Children Trafficking. Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was used to test this hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance and the result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Pearson product moment correlation of unemployment and Women and Children Trafficking

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r-value	Sig.
Unemployment	118	19.41	2.39	0.548**	.000
Women and children trafficking	118	18.96	2.05		

*significant at 0.05 level; df = 116 critical r value = 0.098

Source: Field survey, 2019.

The result in Table 4 revealed that the calculated r – value of 0.548** is greater than the critical r-value of 0.098 at 0.05 level of significance with 116 degrees of freedom. By this result, the null hypothesis which states that, Unemployment does not significantly correlates with Trafficking in women and children in Calabar; Cross River State, Nigeria is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted. The correlation coefficient is a standardized measure of an observed effect, it is a commonly used measure of the size of an effect and that values of ± 1 represent a small effect, ± 3 is a medium effect and ± 5 is a large effect.

The squared correlation $(0.548)^2$ which is a measure of effect size indicates the proportion of explained variance on the dependent variable. Therefore, 30.0% of the variance in Trafficking in women and children is accounted for by unemployment. The magnitude of effect is large, we can conclude that, Unemployment significantly correlates with Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria.

8. Conclusion and Recommendation

The objective of the study is to examine those Associate factors of trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. The study specifically examined the extent to which lack of basic amenities and unemployment relates to Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. Results from the analysis of data revealed that there is a strong significant relationship between lack of basic amenities, unemployment and Trafficking in women and children in Calabar, Cross River State, and Nigeria. Human trafficking is a problem that is linked larger, global processes. It is not simply a social or moral problem to be treated with casual initiatives, as they do not address lack of basic amenities or related issues of vulnerability and

discrimination in strategic or sustainable ways. Trafficking is a development concern, which requires a balanced, layered and integrated approach, built on a foundation of rights-based principles and standards. Prevention requires long-term thinking and interventions on three levels, primary (stopping things before they happen), secondary (limiting the number of cases that occur) and tertiary (limiting the extent of the cases and their damaging impact).

Based on this the following recommendations are made;

- 1) The governments should make efforts towards the reduction of poverty in the land. Skill acquisition should be promoted and small loans be made available for eligible persons.
- 2) The government of cross River State should encourage parents' involvement in cooperative societies through which they will be empowered for economic self-reliance. This approach will help to reduce the poverty level of parents who are enticed to patronize human trafficking.
- 3) The government should expand the job market and make employment available to single or unmarried youths to help the care for themselves and think less of migrating away from their State.

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